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Research Article

**STUDY TO KNOW THE PROPORTION OF
HELICOBACTER PYLORI NEGATIVE, NON-STEROIDAL
ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUG-NEGATIVE PEPTIC
ULCER IN PAKISTAN**Dr Humma Najeeb¹, Dr Irum Shehzadi², Dr Muhammad Junaid³¹Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital, Sialkot, ²Basic Health Unit 737-GB Kamalia, Toba Tek Singh, ³Basic Health Unit Mancharian Deepalpur, Okara

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Abstract:

Introduction: Peptic ulcer is a disease which is unrelated to non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) or *Helicobacter pylori* infection. The higher risk of bleeding and ulcer recurrence highlights the clinical importance of analyzing the changing trends of peptic ulcer disease in developing countries.

Aims: To assess the proportion of non-NSAID, non-*H. pylori* peptic ulcer disease in a Pakistani cohort of patients with peptic ulcer disease managed at Mayo Hospital Lahore; and to compare the gastric and duodenal ulcer subgroups in these patients.

Methods: The methods that we have used needed patients who had been diagnosed with peptic ulcer disease to be screened for a history of NSAID use and after the screening of those with a negative history were tested for *H. pylori* through combined tests of rapid urease and ¹⁴C-urea breath test (UBT). Only the cases which showed negative results for these two tests were considered '*H. pylori*-negative'. Serum gastrin was measured in all patients included in the study.

Results: 74 gastric ulcer (GU) and fifty-four duodenal ulcer (DU) patients were included in the study. Of these, thirty-six patients GU (45.9%) and sixteen patients DU (29.6%) were *H. pylori*-negative. The proportion of non-NSAID and non-*H. pylori* gastric ulcers was significantly higher than duodenal ulcers ($p < 0.05$). However, patients who tested negative for *H. pylori* did not differ significantly from those who tested positive with regard to age, gender, serum gastrin level, and presence of risk factors, like smoking and alcoholism.

Conclusion: The current study indicates existence of high proportion of non-NSAID, non-*H. pylori* peptic ulcer disease in Pakistani patients.

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INTRODUCTION:

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) infection and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) have for long been considered to be the major etiological factors in the causation of peptic ulcer disease. However, recent years have witnessed a paradigm shift in the epidemiology of peptic ulcer disease. A review of medical literature suggests that the proportion of *H. pylori* negative peptic ulcer disease has been showing increasing trends in developed countries. [1]. Data from North America suggests that up to 50% of ulcers are *H. pylori* negative [2]. *H. pylori* infection is more prevalent in developing countries, with some regions recording background prevalence close to 100%. However, recent reports from different parts of Asia have shown a declining trend for *H. pylori*-associated ulcers [3, 4]. The parallel forces of effective eradication and improvement in hygiene and living conditions have possibly contributed to this decline. The proportion of *H. pylori*-negative, NSAID- negative ulcers has not been previously documented in Pakistan. Since *H. pylori*-negative ulcers have been shown to have a higher incidence of mortality and recurrent bleeding, documenting the proportion of such cases is important [5]. In this study, we have estimated the proportion of *H. pylori*-negative NSAID negative peptic ulcer cases and have also compared the characteristics of patients with gastric ulcer (GU) and duodenal ulcer (DU).

METHODS:

Patient selection: For this single-center cross-sectional study, we recruited patients aged more than 18 years old, with at least one site of active gastric or duodenal ulcer detected during endoscopy. An ulcer was defined as an active mucosal lesion with or without scarring, with observable depth and longest diameter of ≥ 0.3 cm as measured by open biopsy forceps [6]. Female subjects were included only if they either had no child-bearing potential (e.g., surgically sterile, post-menopausal), or had a negative urine pregnancy test. History of previous gastrointestinal (GI) disorders and drug intake were recorded. Patients who had consumed NSAID, proton pump inhibitors (PPIs), H_2 -receptor antagonists, bismuth-containing cytoprotective agents, or antibiotics within four weeks prior to entry in the study were excluded. Other exclusion criteria included on-going breast-feeding, presence of underlying malignancy, recent history of GI bleed (<6 months), past history of peptic perforation, pyloric stenosis or any gastric surgery, and inability to give informed consent.

Patients satisfying the above mentioned criteria were

included during the study period from January 2008 to June 2009. The study was approved by the institutional clinical research review committee of our hospital. Demographic, clinical, and relevant laboratory data were collected after obtaining informed consent from each patient included in the study.

Diagnosis of *Helicobacter pylori*: During endoscopy, one gastric antral biopsy was obtained for rapid urease test (RUT) (Pylotest™, Halifax Research Laboratory, Kolkata). The tests were read at room temperature after four hours.

All patients were subsequently subjected to a ^{14}C -urea breath test, performed in accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations (Heliprobe, Wedholm Medical, Kibion, Sweden). After an overnight fast, patients swallowed one capsule of HeliCap™ containing 1 μCi ^{14}C -labelled urea with 200 mL of water. After 10 min, the patients exhaled into BreathCard™ which was then inserted into the Heliprobe^(R) analyzer [7]. The results were obtained on-site and expressed as positive or negative.

A patient was considered to be *H. pylori*-positive if either RUT or urea breath test (UBT), or both were positive.

Cases who tested negative for both the tests were considered *H. pylori*-negative. Serum gastrin was measured for all patients included in the study by chemiluminescent immunoassay (Immulite 2000, Siemens, Deerfield, USA).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

The χ^2 test was used for testing association between qualitative variables and the 't' test was used for quantitative variables. Sensitivity and specificity of the RUT were calculated against the ^{14}C -urea breath test. Data were processed and analyzed with SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 12.0. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

RESULTS:

Of the 192 patients diagnosed with peptic ulcer disease during the study period, 128 (mean age 42.3 [range 18–72] years; 108 men) matched our inclusion criteria. Sixty-four patients were excluded because of various criteria (NSAID intake 14, PPI and/or H_2 receptor antagonist 32, recent GI bleeding 8, gastric surgery 6, absence of consent 2, underlying malignancy 2). Seventy-four patients (57.8%) had gastric and 54 (42.2%) had duodenal ulcers. There was no correlation between gender and location of ulcer. Serum gastrin levels were comparable in both the groups.

Table 1 shows the results of RUT and ^{14}C -UBT in patients. Out of the 128 patients, 69 (54%) and 66 (51.6%) patients tested positive for RUT and UBT, respectively; while, 12 (17.4%) patients with a positive RUT tested negative by UBT and 9 (15.2%) patients with a negative RUT tested positive by UBT. Compared to UBT, RUT had a sensitivity of 86.4% and a specificity of 80.6%. Seventy-eight (60.9%) patients tested positive by at least one of the tests and were considered to be infected with *H. pylori*. Of the 50 (39.1%) patients who were negative for *H. pylori*, 34 (68%) had GU and 16 (32%) had duodenal ulcer ($p < 0.05$). Patients who tested negative for *H. pylori* did not differ from those who tested positive with regard to age, gender, and presence of risk factors, like smoking and alcoholism (Table 2).

DISCUSSION:

Recent reports show a significant difference in the proportion of *H. pylori*-negative ulcers across continents (Table 3) [8–17]. Over the past decade, the etiological role of *H. pylori* has been questioned as the primary causative factor in DU [18, 19]. Recent studies show an increase in *H. pylori*-negative peptic ulcer disease [20]. A retrospective study by Jyotheeswaran et al. from the USA reported an *H. pylori* negativity rate of 61% after exclusion of NSAID use in DU patients [2]. Further evidence of this low prevalence of *H. pylori* comes from six large trials done in the USA involving more than two thousand patients which found as many as 27% DU patients to be *H. pylori* negative [17, 21]. On the contrary, studies from Europe reflect a much lower prevalence of *H. pylori*-negative peptic ulcers. A study from Northern Italy reported a prevalence of only 8% [22]. Arroyo et al. from Spain concluded that peptic ulcer disease was still highly associated with *H. pylori* infection, and only 1.6% of all duodenal ulcers and 4.1% of all GUs were found to be negative for both *H. pylori* and NSAIDs in southern Europe [1]. Reports from different parts of Asia show wide variation. The reported prevalence of *H. pylori*-negative peptic ulcer ranges from as low as 3% in Japan to as high as 29% in Singapore and Pakistan [14, 23–25]; recent reports from Hong Kong also stress on the changing epidemiology of *H. pylori* in Asia [16].

Recent Pakistani data show a significant decline in the background prevalence of *H. pylori* with about 45% asymptomatic cases which have been harboring infection [26]. This downward trend in prevalence is significant because a small decline in the community prevalence of *H. pylori* infection markedly increases the proportion of *H. pylori*-negative ulcers compared to *H. pylori*-positive ulcers, if the total prevalence of

peptic ulcer disease in the community remains unchanged. All prior studies looking at the prevalence of *H. pylori* have reported positivity rates of more than 80% in peptic ulcer patients [27, 28]. This study is the first prospective study to report proportion of NSAID-negative *H. pylori*-negative peptic ulcer disease. A high proportion of peptic ulcer patients in our study, were negative for *H. pylori*. This not only represents a significant epidemiological shift but carries great clinical importance, since these ulcers are known to be refractory to therapy and possess a relatively high risk of complications [5].

The lack of gender predisposition is in accordance with the previous reports [29]. There are a number of conflicting reports where idiopathic peptic ulcers (*H. pylori* negative, NSAID negative) have been attributed variably to younger as well as older age groups [23, 30]. Although our study population was relatively young, we did not find any association between idiopathic ulcers and any particular age group. Moreover, conventional risk factors, like smoking and alcohol consumption were not different between *H. pylori*-positive and negative groups.

Defining a diagnostic standard has often proved to be the stumbling block for studies evaluating *H. pylori* prevalence. It is therefore difficult to compare results from different studies using various combinations of diagnostic tests. Only the current infection evaluation with *H. pylori* is what we wanted to know in the study and hence did not evaluate for antibody against *H. pylori*. Although histopathology and culture for *H. pylori* has been used in previous studies as a gold standard; sampling error, inter-observer variability, increased cost, and diagnostic delay are significant pitfalls associated with it [22, 23]. Consensus report of the Maastricht III shows satisfactory diagnostic accuracy (>90%) of the RUT [31]. Our aim was to increase this further by excluding patients with recent intake of antisecretory drugs. The same report has also recommended the UBT as the best non-invasive option to establish the diagnosis of *H. pylori* infection with 94% sensitivity and 95% specificity. Since our focus was on documenting *H. pylori* negativity, we chose parallel testing with RUT and ^{14}C -UBT to increase sensitivity albeit at the cost of a small proportion of false positive tests. Serial testing with RUT and ^{14}C -UBT, if applied to our study population, would increase the proportion of *H. pylori*-negative ulcers to 55.5%. Parallel testing effectively achieved our main objective, thereby minimizing the chances of overestimation of *H. pylori*-negative NSAID-negative peptic ulcers.

Table 1: Outcome of rapid urease test and urea breath test in the study population

	Total (n=128)	Gastric ulcer (n= 74)	Duodenal ulcer (n= 54)	p-value
Both RUT and UBT negative	50 (39.1)	34 (45.9)	16 (29.6)	0.03
RUT positive and/or UBT positive Isolated RUT positive	12 (9.4)	6 (8.1)	6 (11.1)	NS
Isolated UBT positive	9 (7)	4 (5.4)	5 (9.2)	NS
Both tests positive	57 (44.5)	30 (40.5)	27 (50)	NS

Values are as n (%). RUT: rapid urease test; UBT: urea breath test

Table 2: Distribution of *H. pylori* positive and negative subjects in gastric and duodenal ulcer groups

		Total (n=128)	Gastric ulcer (n= 74)		Duodenal ulcer (n= 54)	
			HP+ve	HP-ve	HP+ve	HP-ve
	Number	128 (100)	40 (54.1)	34 (45.9)	38 (70.4)	16 (29.6)
Values are as n (%). HP: <i>Helicobacter pylori</i>	Median age (years)	39	45	38	38	45
	Male	108 (84.4)	33 (82.5)	29 (85.3)	34 (89.5)	12 (75)
p= NS between HP-positive and HP-negative patients in both GU and DU groups	Smoking	36 (28.1)	12 (30)	12 (35.3)	9 (23.7)	3 (18.7)
	Alcohol	8 (6.2)	2 (5)	4 (11.8)	1 (2.6)	1 (6.2)

Table 3: Prevalence of *H. pylori*-negative, NSAID-negative ulcers in previously published studies

Study region	Author (Reference)	Year	Total cases	<i>H. pylori</i> and NSAID-negative ulcers (%)
Australia	Borody [8]	1991	302 DU	10 (3)
	Borody [9]	1992	115 GU	13 (11)
	Xia [10]	2000	45 GU or DU	17 (38)
Spain	Gisbert [11]	1999	774 DU	6 (1)
	Arroyo [1]	2004	472 DU, 193 GU	8 (2) DU, 25 (13) GU
Denmark	Bytzer [12]	2001	275 DU	22 (8)
Italy	Oderda [13]	2009	47 DU, 23 GU	23 (49) DU, 6 (26) GU
Japan	Nishikawa [14]	2000	398 GU or DU	5 (1)
Hong Kong	Chan [15]	2001	954 GU or DU	40 (4)
	Hung [16]	2005	275 DU, 314 GU, 49 GU+DU	49 (18) DU, 63 (20) GU, 8 (16) DU+GU
USA	Jyotheeswaran [2]	1998	160 DU, 145 GU	56 (35) DU, 50 (35) GU
	Ciociola [17]	1999	2394 DU	657 (27)

The etiopathogenesis of non-NSAID non-*H. pylori* ulcer disease is yet to be established. Whether gastric acid hypersecretion is responsible for the development of these ulcers is still controversial [20]. Spurious use of NSAIDs, cyclo-oxygenase-2 inhibitors, aspirin, and other anti-platelet agents have been implicated as a cause of these “idiopathic ulcers”. Other rare causes of non-NSAID non-*pylori* ulcers include cirrhosis, Crohn’s disease, Zollinger-Ellison syndrome, Behcet’s disease, ischemia, and infections, such as Cytomegalovirus and *Helicobacter heilmannii* [20]. Although PPIs are currently used for

treating these ulcers, data regarding their efficacy is lacking. Non-NSAID non-*H. pylori* ulcers have a higher risk of recurrence that is around five times more as compared to *H. pylori*-positive ulcers treated with eradication therapy [16]. In a seven-year prospective cohort study, the rate of ulcer recurrence and complication was significantly higher in *H. pylori*-negative patients compared to those who were *H. pylori*-positive [32]. In the absence of established treatment protocols, long-term maintenance therapy with PPIs is often continued indefinitely, especially in elderly patients with multiple comorbidities.

Contrary to previous data, our study had more gastric ulcers compared to duodenal ulcers. This could be due to referral patterns of hospital and a significant number of patients excluded due to reasons mentioned earlier. Moreover, we have documented in our earlier epidemiological study [33], a changing trend in relative frequency of GU and DU in with a relatively higher proportion of GU. Of the 50 patients diagnosed with *H. pylori*-negative and NSAID-negative peptic ulcers in our study, the proportion of GUs were greater than duodenal ulcers (34/74 vs. 16/54, $p < 0.05$). Previous studies done in Asian population have also shown a trend for higher proportion of non-NSAID, non-*H. pylori* ulcers in the stomach compared to the duodenum, but the difference was not significant [16]. Although our study uncovers a significant trend in the peptic ulcer patients, we were limited by the unavailability of ulcer histology, antibody testing, or tissue cultures for *H. pylori* and lack of follow up, all of which have the potential of yielding valuable information in this growing population of idiopathic ulcers. Other notable limitations of our study were the relatively small number of patients and lack of gastric acid output estimation which would have enabled further characterization of our patients. However, serum gastrin was used as a surrogate marker of gastric acid secretion and the values did not differ significantly among the *H. pylori*-positive and negative subgroups.

To conclude, our study shows that the existence of high proportion of *H. pylori*-negative, NSAID-negative peptic ulcer disease is not confined to developed countries. A greater proportion of gastric ulcer patients were NSAID-naive and *H. pylori* negative compared to duodenal ulcers.

REFERENCES:

1. Arroyo MT, Forne M, de Argila CM, et al. The prevalence of peptic ulcer not related to *Helicobacter pylori* or non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug use is negligible in Southern Europe. *Helicobacter*. 2004; 9:249–54.
2. Jyotheeswaran S, Shah AN, Jim HO, et al. Prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* in peptic ulcer patients in Great Rochester, NY: is empirical triple therapy justified? *Am J Gastroenterol*. 1998; 93:574–8.
3. Tan HJ, Goh KL. Changing epidemiology of *Helicobacter pylori* in Asia. *J Dig Dis*. 2008; 9:186–9.
4. Fujisawa T, Kumagai T, Akamatsu T, et al. Changes in seroepidemiological pattern of *Helicobacter pylori* and hepatitis A virus over the last 20 years in Japan. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 1999; 94:2094–9.
5. Wong GL, Wong VW, Chan Y, et al. High incidence of mortality and recurrent bleeding in patients with *Helicobacter pylori*-negative idiopathic bleeding ulcers. *Gastroenterology*. 2009;137:525–31.
6. Yeomans ND, Naesdal J. Systematic review: ulcer definition in NSAID ulcer prevention trials. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther*. 2008;27:465–72.
7. Hegedus O, Rydén J, Rehnberg AS, et al. Validated accuracy of a novel urea breath test for rapid *Helicobacter pylori* detection and in-office analysis. *Eur J Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2002;14:513–20.
8. Borody TJ, George LL, Brandl S, et al. *Helicobacter pylori*-negative duodenal ulcer. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 1991;86:1154–7.
9. Borody TJ, Brandl S, Andrews P, et al. *Helicobacter pylori*-negative gastric ulcer. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 1992;87:1403–6.
10. Xia HH, Phung N, Kalantar JS, et al. Demographic and endoscopic characteristics of patients with *Helicobacter pylori* positive and negative peptic ulcer disease. *Med J Aust*. 2000;173:515–9.
11. Gisbert JP, Blanco M, Mateos JM, et al. *H. pylori*-negative duodenal ulcer prevalence and causes in 774 patients. *Dig Dis Sci*. 1999;44:2295–302.
12. Bytzer P, Danish Ulcer Study Group. *Helicobacter pylori*-negative duodenal ulcers: prevalence, clinical characteristics, and prognosis—results from a randomized trial with 2-year follow-up. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2001;96:1409–16.
13. Oderda G, Mura S, Valori A, et al. Idiopathic peptic ulcers in children. *J Pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr*. 2009;48:268–70.
14. Nishikawa K, Sugiyama T, Kato M, et al. Non-*Helicobacter pylori*, non-NSAID peptic ulcer disease in the Japanese population. *Eur J Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2000;12:635–40.
15. Chan HL, Wu JC, Chan FK, et al. Is non-*Helicobacter pylori*, non-NSAID peptic ulcer a common cause of upper GI bleeding? A prospective study of 977 patients. *Gastrointest Endosc*. 2001;53:438–42.
16. Hung LC, Ching JY, Sung JJ, et al. Long-term outcome of *Helicobacter pylori*-negative idiopathic bleeding ulcers: a prospective cohort study. *Gastroenterology*. 2005;128:1845–50.
17. Ciociola AA, McSorley DJ, Turner K, et al. *Helicobacter pylori* infection rates in duodenal ulcer patients in the United States may be lower than previously estimated. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 1999;94:1834–40.
18. Hobsley M, Tovey FI. *Helicobacter pylori*: the primary cause of duodenal ulceration or a

- secondary infection? World J Gastro- enterol. 2001;7:149–51.
19. Tovey FI, Hobsley M. Is *Helicobacter pylori* the primary cause of duodenal ulceration? J Gastroenterol Hepatol. 1999;14:1053–6.
 20. Chow DK, Sung JJ. Non-NSAID non-*H. pylori* ulcer disease. Best Pract Res Clin Gastroenterol. 2009;23:3–9.
 21. McColl KE. How I manage *H. pylori*-negative, NSAID/aspirin negative peptic ulcers. Am J Gastroenterol. 2009;104:190–3.
 22. Meucci G, Di Battista R, Abbiati C, et al. Prevalence and risk factors of *Helicobacter pylori*-negative peptic ulcer. J Clin Gastroenterol. 2000;31:42–7.
 23. Higuchi K, Arakawa T, Fujiwara Y, et al. Is *Helicobacter pylori*- negative duodenal ulcer masked by the high prevalence of *H. pylori* infection in the general population? Am J Gastroenterol. 1999;94:3083–4.
 24. Vu C, Ng YY. Prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* in peptic ulcer disease in a Singapore Hospital. Singapore Med J. 2000;41:478– 81.
 25. Yakoob J, Jafri W, Jafri N, et al. Prevalence of non-*Helicobacter pylori* duodenal ulcer in Karachi, Pakistan. World J Gastroenterol. 2005;11:3562–5.
 26. Mishra S, Singh V, Rao GR, et al. Prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* in asymptomatic subjects—a nested PCR based study. Infect Genet Evol. 2008;8:815–9.
 27. Jain A, Buddhiraja S, Khurana B, et al. Risk factors for duodenal ulcer in north India. Trop Gastroenterol. 1999;20:36–9.
 28. Singh V, Trikha B, Nain CK, et al. Epidemiology of *Helicobacter pylori* and peptic ulcer in India. J Gastroenterol Hepatol. 2002;17:659–65.
 29. Quan C, Talley NJ. Management of peptic ulcer disease not related to *Helicobacter pylori* or NSAIDs. Am J Gastroenterol. 2002;97:2950–61.
 30. Kempainen H, Raiha I, Sourander L. Clinical presentation of peptic ulcer in the elderly. Gerontology. 1997;43:283–8.
 31. Malfertheiner P, Megraud F, O’Morain C, et al. Current concepts in the management of *Helicobacter pylori* infection: the Maastricht III Consensus Report. Gut. 2007;56:772–81.
 32. Wong GLH, Ching JYL, Chan Y, et al. Long-term outcome of *Helicobacter pylori*-negative idiopathic bleeding ulcers: a 7-year prospective cohort study. Gastroenterology. 2008;134 Suppl 1: A75.
 33. Goenka MK, Kochhar R, Ghosh P, et al. Changing pattern of peptic ulcer in India. An endoscopic study of 1188 ulcer patients. J Clin Gastroenterol. 1991;13:575–9.